

SEVERITY OF DENGUE AND ITS COMPLICATION ASSOCIATED WITH PATIENTS' BLOOD GROUP

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Abstract

Objective: To determine frequency of different severities of dengue fever complications in patients with different blood groups.

Study design: Analytical, cross-sectional study

Place and duration of Study: Department of internal medicine, Fazaia Ruth Pfau Medical College PAF Base Faisal, Karachi, from October' 2024 to May'2025

Methodology: After approval of study from Institutional Review Board (IRB), we studied 142 dengue positive patients collected through non-probability consecutive sampling to compare frequency of different severities of dengue fever complications in patients with different blood groups.

Results: The primary outcome was the frequency of different severities of dengue fever complications in patients with different blood. The most prevalent group was blood group B and among all Gp-B patients, 18 (94.7%) developed moderate complications and 1(5.3%) developed severe complications while none of the patients developed very severe complications with p value <0.001. The most prevalent blood group to develop Dengue complications was blood group O-positive with 4(50.0%) patients with severe disease and 4 (50.0%) patients with severe disease. None of group O-patients had moderate disease. The least prevalent blood group type was AB-positive. None of the patients developed severe diseases and all patients (75.0%) developed moderate disease with p value <0.001.

Conclusion: We concluded that blood group B-positive was the most prevalent among dengue patients, while individuals with O-positive blood group demonstrated a higher susceptibility to severe manifestations of the disease.

INTRODUCTION

Dengue is the most common arthropod-borne virus which has become a serious threat to global health with almost 8 million confirmed cases in the year 2024.¹ Dengue fever (DF), dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF), and dengue shock syndrome (DSS) are grim complications of dengue fever.² Despite serious sequels, the burden of dengue fever is globally underestimated, undetected, misdiagnosed and under-reported. An important association of Dengue fever with blood typing is also un-documented and not-studied extensively.

Kaipainen and Vuorinen originally proposed the link between blood types and disease in 1960.³ It is already established that ABO blood type dictates an individual's susceptibility or resistance to illnesses like cancer, cognitive disorders, malaria, metabolic diseases, cognitive and circulatory disorders. Dengue is also recently included in the list of these diseases.⁴ The knowledge of susceptibility of certain blood groups to dengue severity can help create preventive and control designs to contain this disease which is showing active transmission in more than ninety countries worldwide including Pakistan.

There are contradictions in the already published literature regarding the relationship between blood group and dengue severity. Some authors advocate B-blood group is more susceptible to complications of dengue fever⁵ while other authors have hypothesized that AB-blood group is more susceptible⁶ and some authors believe that O-positive blood group is linked to dengue severity.⁷ Furthermore, despite international evidence, very little information about the association between dengue severity and blood group has been published in local studies. There has been a widespread dengue outbreak in Pakistani cities in recent years,⁸ and the number of cases is increasing every year. Therefore, the rationale is to present data regarding our demographic population, verify the relationship between blood groups and severity of disease and share our experience with rest of world. We intend to create awareness of this important but seemingly overlooked and underrated relationship.

Methodology:

After seeking the approval of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of our hospital with

registration# FRPMC-IRB-2024-68, we performed this research at the department of internal medicine Fazaia Ruth Pfau Medical College Karachi. The study was carried out over a period of six months from January-July, 2025. We estimated the sample with help of Open-Epi sample size calculator. A previously conducted study reported that the prevalence of severe DF was 10%⁹ in susceptible dengue patients. Using 95% confidence interval and 5% precision, sample size came out to be 139. Sample size estimation was performed on the online available calculator Open-Epi.

Inclusion criteria:

Individuals of age 15 years and above of either gender admitted with NS-1 positive within 48 hours of positive result. Exclusion criteria: pediatric patients (<15 years), Patients with coexisting malaria, leptospirosis or any fever with Dengue NS negative, Patients presenting after 7 seven days of symptoms onset, Patients with known liver disease with positive HBsAg, HAVe or HEV pregnant females, patients with diabetes mellitus, Hypertension, decompensated cardiac disease, asthma, chronic liver, kidney or pulmonary disease, patients with malignancy or any blood dyscrasias. The sample was collected through non-probability consecutive sampling. The study will be performed after acquiring formal permission from the hospital ethics committee. The sample of dengue positive cases will be collected by non-probability consecutive sampling based on inclusion criteria furnished. The blood grouping of all patients will be performed, and they will be followed till recovery or development of any complication. The patients who develop mild dengue marked by fever with presence or absence of any associated symptoms including headache, peri-orbital pain, myalgia, vomiting or mild rash controlled with symptomatic treatment and recovery occurs within two weeks were rendered to be complication free and will be grouped as group-A. The patients who will have delayed recovery and will develop complications will be grouped as group-B. Three grades of severity will be devised based on complications labelled Moderate, severe and very severe. Moderate: Features of mild dengue with addition of warning signs including one or more of the following: severe

abdominal discomfort or pain, persistent vomiting, ascites, pleural effusion, bleeding from mucosa, hepatomegaly \geq 2-centimeter, thrombocytopenia (platelet count \leq 150) or increase in hematocrit (20% from baseline) or lethargy. Severe: Features of mild or moderate dengue accompanied by one or more of

following: Hemorrhage, impaired consciousness, myocardial dysfunction, pulmonary dysfunction or organ dysfunction or/and liver enzymes \geq 1000 international units/ liter. Very severe: Features of severe dengue with dengue shock syndrome (hypotension or absent blood pressure and hemorrhagic manifestations including hematemesis, hematochezia and menorrhagia¹⁰. We will record the following demographic details of all patients. age

group (15-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-55, 56-65, 66-75 and greater than 76), gender, BMI and addiction (smoking, niswar or hukkah). The primary outcome will be the frequency of different blood groups in group-A (complication free patients) and group-B (patients with complications). The severity grades of dengue complications will be compared between different blood group types in group-B patients. The data will be processed and analyzed through statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) version 26. All quantitative and qualitative variables will be subjected to descriptive statistics by using appropriate tests. Chi-square analysis will be used to compare grades of severity between different blood types. p value less than 0.05 will be considered significant.

Figure-1: Phases of Study: Consort Diagram

Results:

A Total of 142 patients completed study protocol. There were 98 patients who did not develop any complications, and they were included in Gp-A and 44 patients who developed complications and were

grouped together as Gp-B. The demographic variables were similar between both groups. In Gp-A there were 68 (69.4%) patients with age between 15-25 years, 30 (30.6%) patients had age between 26-35 years, 28 (28.6%) patients with age between 36-45

years, 14 (14.3%) patients with age between 46-55 years, 27 (27.6%) patients with age between 56-65 years and 1 (1.0%) patient with age between 66-75 years. The most prevalent age group in Gp-B was between 26-35 years and the least prevalent was 46-55 years with p value 0.182. There were 68 (69.4%)

males in Gp-A and 25 (56.8) males in Gp-B. There were 30 (30.6%) females in Gp-A and 19 (43.2%) females in Gp-B with male predominance. The most common BMI was 21-24 Kg/m² which was measured in 66 (67.3) Gp-A patients and 27 (61.4%) Gp-B patients. The demographics are given in Table-I. The primary outcome was the frequency of different severities of dengue fever complications in patients with different blood groups. The distribution of blood groups between both groups was significantly different. In Gp-A, 36 (36.7%) had blood group A-positive, 22 (22.4%) patients had blood group B-positive, 20 (20.4%) had blood group O-positive and

20 (20.4%) patients had blood group AB-positive. In Gp-B, 11 (25.0%) had blood group A-positive, 21 (47.7%) patients had blood group B-positive, 8 (18.2%) had blood group O-positive and 4 (9.1%) patients had blood group AB-positive. The most prevalent group was blood group B and among all Gp-B patients, 18 (94.7%) developed moderate complications and 1 (5.3%) developed severe complications while none of the patients developed very severe complications with p value <0.001. The most prevalent blood group to develop Dengue complications was blood group O-positive with 4 (50.0%) patients with severe disease and 4 (50.0%) patients with moderate disease. None of group O-patients had moderate disease. The least prevalent blood group type was AB-positive. None of the patients developed severe diseases and all patients (75.0%) developed moderate disease with p value <0.001.

Table-I: The demographic characteristics of population sample (n=142)

		Gp-A n=98	Gp-B n=44	p value
Age (years)	15-25	68 (69.4)	0 (0)	0.182
	26-35	30 (30.6)	14 (31.8)	
	36-45	28 (28.6)	13 (29.5)	
	46-55	14 (14.3)	5 (11.4)	
	56-65	27 (27.6)	12 (27.3)	
	66-75	1 (1.0)	0 (0)	
Gender	male	68 (69.4)	25 (56.8)	0.103
	female	30 (30.6)	19 (43.2)	
BMI (Kg/m ²)	18-20	4 (4.1)	3 (6.8)	0.432
	21-24	66 (67.3)	27 (61.4)	
	25-30	22 (22.4)	8 (18.2)	
	31-35	6 (6.1)	6 (13.6)	
Addiction	Hukka smoker	6 (6.1)	1 (2.3)	
	Cigarette smoker	5 (5.1)	3 (6.8)	
	Niswar addict	10 (10.2)	4 (9.1)	
	No addiction	77 (78.6)	36 (81.8)	

Table-II: Frequencies of blood groups and Comparison of dengue fever complications between patients of different blood group types (n=142)

Frequency of different blood group types in Gp-A and Gp-B			
Blood group	Gp-A n=98	Gp-B n=44	p value
A-positive	36 (36.7)	13 (43.2)	0.019

B-positive	22 (22.4)	19(43.2)			
O- positive	20 (20.4)	8 (18.2)			
AB- positive	20 (20.4)	4 (9.1)			
Comparison of frequency of dengue severity grades with blood types in Gp-B (n=44)					
Dengue severity	Gp-B n=44				p value
	A-positive n=13	B-positive n=19	O-positive n=8	AB-positive n=4	
Moderate	13 (100.0)	18 (94.7)	4 (50.0)	4 (100.0)	<0.001
Severe	0 (0)	1 (5.3)	4 (50.0)	0 (0)	
Very Severe	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	

Discussion:

Our study showed that B-positive blood group was the most prevalent blood group. The dengue fever affected relatively younger age groups more than older age groups and its severity was highest in patients with O-positive blood. According to Naveed Iqbal,¹¹ young adult males are affected by Dengue likely due to greater outdoor exposure. They established that Group B was the most frequent blood group among dengue positive patients, but they could not develop clear association between blood group and disease severity. They noted Significant gender differences in laboratory markers highlighting possible sex-based variations in clinical presentation and disease progression. We presented that O-positive patients were more likely to develop complications and AB positive were less likely to develop disease severity which was not analogous to their findings.

The systematic review and meta-analysis by Mohammad Rashidul Hashan et al¹² highlighted a significant association between ABO blood groups and the severity of dengue infection. Their findings consistently showed that individuals with blood group O are at a heightened risk of developing both dengue fever (DF) and its more severe form, dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF), compared to other blood groups. They ranked the risk as group O followed by B, A, and AB and suggested that a gradient of susceptibility could be influenced by underlying immune-hematological mechanisms. Our study suggested that blood group O had the highest incidence of complications but in their study, it was second most common. We cannot generalize the findings of their study for our study population.

According to Siripen Kalayanarooj et al¹³, blood group AB has potential risk factors for severe dengue, particularly in individuals experiencing a secondary infection. They advocated that Patients with AB blood type were significantly more likely to develop grade three dengue hemorrhagic fever compared to those with milder forms or dengue fever. Although their suggested a possible interaction between ABO blood antigens and the host immune response but their data on association of AB-positive blood group with dengue did not show similarity to rest of literature. As in our study, AB positive was least affected by dengue. Moreover, their findings were not supported by other authors like Tahmina Akhter et al¹⁴ who established that the highest number of dengue-positive cases were observed in individuals with O-positive blood group followed by group B-positive. In our study the most prevalent blood type was B in dengue affected patients but group O-positive developed a more severe disease. The possible explanation is that blood groups B-positive has highest prevalence in Pakistan.¹⁵

A local study by Shaheen Kouser¹⁶ et al highlighted a notable association between blood group O and increased susceptibility to dengue fever (DF), suggesting that individuals with this blood type may face a higher risk of infection compared to other groups. Their analysis showed a greater prevalence of group O among dengue patients, particularly in males and across all age groups, with a significant proportion experiencing severe thrombocytopenia. Our study showed that B positive was most prevalent among the population but most notable in developing dengue complications was group O-positive. Group B-positive was the second most

common blood type to develop higher severity of complications in our study. Our findings are aligned with the findings of Shaheen kouser study. The conflicting evidence was provided by Bulugahapitiya¹⁷ who reviewed 183 suspected dengue cases Sri Lankan patients. They showed that 58% of severe cases had B positive blood group. The most prevalent blood group in their study group was O positive. Their findings were just opposite to our study. In another study of Asian origin done on Sri Lankan¹⁸ population revealed there is a significant link between ABO blood groups and dengue severity ($p < 0.001$). Patients with blood group AB had over 2.5 times higher risk of developing DHF, while those with blood group O were less likely to develop severe dengue, suggesting a protective effect of group O against DHF. Our study showed that AB-positive blood had the lowest frequency of complications due to dengue and O-blood group stood highest in severity of disease. In another study¹⁹ on similar demographic population, it was established that Patients with blood group O showed greater susceptibility. No meaningful link was observed between dengue severity or Rh status and ABO grouping, nor was any gender-related trend identified. Authors of a local study²⁰ also observed a marginally increased occurrence of dengue in individuals with blood group O compared and they suggested further investigation to determine the role of ABO and HLA factors in dengue prevalence and severity. The results of our study showed that that B-positive was the most prevalent blood group in both groups and O-positive was most likely to develop serious disease .

Conclusion: We concluded that blood group B-positive was the most prevalent among dengue patients, while individuals with O-positive blood group demonstrated a higher susceptibility to severe manifestations of the disease.

Limitations of Study: It was a single center study. There is need to conduct large-scale prospective cohort on this subject

Conflict of Interest: None

Funding Source: None

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